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The TANGENT Dashboard as a Next Generation Traffic and Transport Management System

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Abstract

The TANGENT project is exploring novel techniques for Dynamic Management of Multimodal Traffic in four European cities. This article provides an overview of the architecture of the TANGENT Tool that is being implemented to support this project. It includes a tour of the Dashboard of the TANGENT Tool, focusing both functional and technical aspects, such as the way data visualisation is made uniform in the platform and how metadata drives the behaviour of different visualisation tools. The TANGENT Tool Planning and Incident Management features are also described, showing how the visualisation features still drive these more advanced use cases such as in Simulation and Cooperative Incident Management. Given this functionality set, a novel platform is proposed, the Next Generation Traffic and Transport Management System.

Keywords: Next-Generation Traffic and Transport Management System, Transport APIs, Multimodal Traffic Management.

Introduction

The TANGENT project [1] is exploring Dynamic Management of Multimodal Traffic in four European cities (Athens, Manchester, Lisbon and Rennes) by creating and trialling a Simulation powered Next-Generation Traffic and Transport Management System.

Transport networks have historically been managed in a segmented way, with each operator managing their own transport mode. Multi-modal cooperation is still more common in aspects like interfacing modes and unifying ticketing, and not so usual at operational and strategic levels. Municipalities and local transport agencies are changing this reality by introducing multi-modal network visualisation, monitorisation and some level of operation. TANGENT intends to materialise this by implementing and trialling a Cooperative Multi-modal Transport Operation tool, referred to as the TANGENT Tool. TANGENT intends to shift cities to multi-modal cooperative transportation operation, acting and planning strategically.

TANGENT is a project funded by the European Commission under the Research and Innovation Programme Horizon 2020. The project started in September 2021 and will end in August 2024. TANGENT is developing

new complementary Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools for optimising traffic and transport operations in a coordinated and dynamic way from a multimodal perspective, considering automated/non-automated vehicles, passengers, and freight transport.

Through the TANGENT Tool and a set of planned trials in each Case Study city, the project will improve knowledge and management of mobility flows along a range of transport modes. In addition, it will enable the implementation and integration of innovative mobility solutions, services, and business models. The project will contribute to more efficient traffic management, facilitating multimodal networks, accelerating the transition towards connected and automated mobility, reducing pollutant emissions and congestion, improving safety and security, and reducing the cost of mobility for all. This a big ambition that starts with a simple, yet, very powerful, ally, data. TANGENT will catalogue, harmonise, store, visualise, augment, forecast, simulate, optimise, and produce consensus, all this starting with live data and traffic models of each city.

The TANGENT Tool

The TANGENT project aims to improve traffic and transport management by implementing three services: Service 1 (S1) provides real-time and forecast information about the network, Service 2 (S2) manages traffic incidents and optimizes network load, and Service 3 (S3) generates operational response plans and simulates scenarios. These services will help transport authorities make informed decisions to improve traffic and passenger flow and reduce congestion [2].

Figure - Top-level TANGENT Tool technical architecture

As mentioned, data is a key element in the TANGENT project. Thus, TANGENT Tool’s Service 0 (depicted as S0 in the previous illustration) had to focus on data. It is responsible for collecting, fusing, and harmonising data from each case study. Service 0 uses a metadata catalogue that contains all the know data sources for each case study. The data is harmonised using and RDF representation [3] and serialized for Service 1 in a JSON format, both following adaptations from standards such as Datex II [4] and SIRI [5].

TANGENT’s Service 1 (depicted as S1 in the previous illustration) includes the TANGENT user interface, a

Dashboard, where operators and managers can access live and predictive information about the roads and transport network. The TANGENT API is also part of Service 1. It receives harmonised data from Service 0, stores and distributes it along the TANGENT Tool. The TANGENT API supports all the features of the Dashboard, namely providing the data that is visualised in the Dashboard and can also be used directly by TANGENT stakeholders to access data. Finally, Service 1 includes a component that further processes and augments data, evaluates data to identify breaches of critical conditions and calculates forecasts based on live data.

Service 2 (depicted as S2 in the previous illustration) is dedicated to Smart Network Load Balancing (SNLB) and Cooperative Incident Management (CIM). These are the features that bring the TANGENT Tool into the arena of Next Generation Traffic and Transport Management (NGTTM). The rationale behind NGTTM is adopting a unified, holistic management of traffic and transport, usually in an urban network, that supports the cooperation between distinct entities involved in planning and managing different types of transport situations such as large events or simpler traffic accidents. NGTTM tools utilize forecast and simulation technology to support operational decisions that will address transport network situations. In TANGENT, both SNLB and CIM materialize the operational stage where a predefined transport anomaly is identified to be occurring live and tools are put in place to address the anomaly according to a predefined response plan. The response plan itself is produced in TANGENT's Service 3 as described in the following paragraph. As for Service 2, both SNLB and CIM are activated when pre-defined triggers/conditions are verified (detection of the anomaly). Next, a Common Operational Picture (COP) will be shown to all the entities involved (in CIM, but just a single user in the case of SNLB). This takes the form of a predefined Dashboard layout that can show maps zoomed into the location of the incident and highlight the most relevant information to follow the situation with. Then, both in CIM and SNLB, a set of predefined response actions need to be reviewed so they can be applied. These actions are respective to the Transport network, and include providing new traffic lights timings, instructions for Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs), adjusting dynamic toll pricings according to congestion levels and, also, information for passengers about specific traffic and transport conditions (e.g., inform about a closed metro line, protests blocking a bus route, usually providing alternatives). Once applied the COP is used to follow the situation resolution.

Service 3 (depicted as S3 in the previous illustration) is responsible for the creation of the Response Plans, used in CIM and SNLB, and supports the simulation of What-if Scenarios. Both types of Response Plans act as templates for response to pre-defined scenarios like a flood in a specific city area or an overload in the metro network. Response Plans contain the relevant information to suggest actions on the transport network to be taken in the context of a CIM or SNLB. The only difference between the two is that the Response Plan for SNLB works with a single stakeholder / entity and doesn't provide coordination mechanisms whereas Cooperative Response Plans for CIM coordinate several stakeholders to support more complex scenarios. Both Response Plans are defined in the TANGENT Dashboard which interacts with Service 3 modules to produce optimised response plan actions and to reach consensus in cooperative decision making. In addition, Service 3 also offers internal TANGENT stakeholders the possibility to execute the simulation of what-if scenarios directly and explore the simulation results in the TANGENT Dashboard.

Let us now take a closer look at the TANGENT modules and how they interact with each other. The TANGENT API is a central element in this project, exchanging data between the different Services. This includes both data coming originally from the cities as well as data supporting communication between the different Services to provide more advanced functionality, such as creating and implementing Response Plans. This central role is illustrated in the following diagram of the TANGENT Tool architecture.

Figure - TANGENT Detailed Technical architecture

Complementing REST and AMQP services

The TANGENT API provides data to both user applications and internal TANGENT services, utilizing both REST and message queue technologies. REST services are utilized for queryable data access, while message queues handle real-time data updates.

REST services are well-suited for user applications due to their ease of implementation and compatibility with existing transportation and smart city API ecosystems. Additionally, REST services are suitable for the TANGENT Dashboard, which relies on them to fetch data for live transport data visualizations.

However, REST services lack the real-time capabilities required for certain TANGENT use cases, such as incident management and data generation. Message queues overcome these limitations by providing a decoupled communication mechanism for real-time data updates.

The TANGENT API utilizes message queues alongside REST services to offer a hybrid solution that combines the best of both worlds. Data is published to the message queue by various services and consumed by both internal and external applications. While a purely message queue-based approach might be more elegant, the queryable nature of REST services and the lack of formal documentation in message queues make the hybrid

approach an asset for the TANGENT API.

A Generic Data-Driven API

To efficiently handle incoming data from various sources, the TANGENT API employs a generic approach that leverages a meta-data framework to define the characteristics of each data source. This approach simplifies data integration and enhances flexibility, allowing the API to seamlessly accommodate new data sources without the need for custom development.

Central to this approach is the meta-data framework, which provides a comprehensive overview of each data source, including its message queue topics, REST base URL, JSON schema, database collections, user permissions, and specific behaviours. This metadata is leveraged to automate data indexing, REST API implementation, and OpenAPI documentation generation, significantly reducing development effort and streamlining the integration process.

Visualisation

The TANGENT user interface is referred to as the TANGENT Dashboard, showing the central role of the Dashboard concept in this user interface. Indeed, most of the TANGENT user interface functionality is delivered through the Dashboard. It was designed to represent both live and forecast data. At the current development stage, it is being used to show live data and forecast data will be added soon. Forecast data will be identified as such to avoid confusion and can thus coexist with live data on the same interface, allowing for direct comparison.

The TANGENT Dashboard is customisable, and this feature will be described further ahead. A typical dashboard will provide live information from both traffic and public transport modes. The example below shows different map views for the city of Manchester. Most of the map views have data limited to the TANGENT case study area depicted by a teal shape around the northwest area of Manchester.

Figure – An example of the TANGENT Dashboard for the city of Manchester

The user interface is divided into four main areas. The top right provides user functionality such as switching city, changing language, or simply showing the current data and time. The left area provides links to all the user interface functionality. The bottom area provides copyright and EU funding information. The dashboard itself has a custom division selected from a set of available possibilities. On the top right four indicators can be seen. These are indicators calculated from traffic data from the case study area and provide a quick view into the status of the case study. This could as easily be done for the entire city. The indicators are colour coded just like the lines on the maps, even using the same thresholds and colour shades. The top left indicator shows the average travel speed. In inner-city areas it is natural that travel speeds go well below 40 km/h because of traffic lights and even the geometry of lanes. The bottom left indicator shows the average flow per section of the road. The right indicators summarize the average road delay and deviation. The travel time delay is calculated from ideal road conditions and quickly allows the detection of problem areas (in the case of a map) or, in the case of an indicator, to understand if traffic is flowing much slower than it would in ideal conditions (with maximum road speeds). It is important to note that all travel times considered are per kilometre, so it is correct to compare two travel time results, calculate averages, etc. The travel time deviation provides an even more valuable indication. It calculates the different between the current travel time and the normal travel time for a typical day at this time. This way it allows detecting locations of probable incidents (accidents, events, etc.) when used with maps and allows understanding if traffic is worse today than it normally would be when used as an indicator.

As for the maps, the top-left map provides color-coded lines depicting the current average speeds in each road segment. On top of this it shows the real-time bus locations and allows the user to get a preview of live traffic cameras. The combination of information, the way it is displayed, and the interactions are fully customisable in the TANGENT Dashboard. The three maps on the bottom area show different measures of traffic flow. The left one shows darker lines when there is more volume of vehicles passing through and lighter ones when there is less volume. The central one shows the travel time delay from ideal road conditions. This is the typical view provided to end-users. And the right-most one shows the travel time deviation, pinpoint accidents as stated. The right-most middle map provides a city-wide view of traffic with data coming from Waze, along with bus locations. In the case of Manchester the option was not to fuse Waze and internal traffic data, internal traffic data was given priority in the Dashboard example used and Waze data as used as a complement, but other options are possible. At this moment Manchester has a Dashboard fully comprised of Waze data, including city-wide indicator summaries.

Any map can be panned, zoomed and expanded for a wider range of view. When zooming out, sometimes the lines become difficult to read, to better summarize the lines information at lower zoom levels the TANGENT Dashboard can automatically switch to a heatmap type visualisation as depicted in the image below.

Figure – Comparison between line and heatmap representation.

In the city of Rennes, it was possible to take the color-coding concept a step further, as there is delay information available for the real-time bus locations. As such, the bus icons could be colour-coded just like road lines were with traffic measurements. Buses which are ahead of schedule appear blue, the ones on schedule appear green, ones with a slight delay appear yellow and with a large delay (15 minutes or more) appear red.

Figure – Map Widget from the City of Rennes.

Figure – Colour gradient used for the colour-coding of bus icons according to delay.

It is also noticeable that in the city of Rennes the option was not to filter the traffic information to the area of the case study. Alongside the typical traffic indicators, which in this case are city-wide (thus have higher speed values), there is also an indicator of the average public transport delay. Naturally it is colour-coded just like the

bus icons on the map.

Customisation

The TANGENT Tool is designed to easily allow the introduction of new data sources. The representation of these new data sources is also part of this lean process. The TANGENT Dashboard customisation features are powerful enough to support the introduction of new data sources as well as allow managers to enhance existing visualisations or easily create new visualisations, for example, to support the Common Operational Picture (COP) for specific events. Each city / case study can have one or more Dashboards, only managers can create these Dashboards, but any user can select one of these Dashboards for use. Creating a new Dashboard starts with the selection of a layout from a set of layouts available. After this selection the Dashboard is ready to receive content. Content is dragged into the dashboard areas in the form of Widgets which are visible in a vertical list right of the Dashboards. The image below shows this process and was captured while a Road Travel Time Delay Widget was being dragged into this dashboard.

Figure – Dashboard Customizer.

There are three different types of Widgets in the TANGENT Tool: Map Widgets, Indicator Widgets and Table Widgets. The first two have already been extensively exemplified, the latter is a simple Widget type that can be used to show tables with data. Widgets can be created, just like Dashboards. The process starts by selecting the type of Widget and then setting Widget specific data. The most complex one is the Map Widget. The map can be panned and zoomed to the location of interest, or the corresponding properties can be set on the Widget Builder.

Figure – Map Widget Builder.

Next, a Base Map can be selected from a set of Base Map available. Light or Dark minimal maps work better with the need to emphasize dynamic color-coded content on the map. Finally, the layers of the map are chosen from a set of predefined layers and ordered to define which layers appear on the top / front.

It would be possible to have a user interface to define the Layers from available data, but the option was to do this as a database configuration instead. A collection of all the Layers available contains information on each one, defining the source of the data (one source per layer), how the data is represented (either as a line, a shape, a point), the style used to represent it and how the style changes according to data values, when should a heatmap be used to represent the data and how interactions with the data work, namely what is done when the data is clicked. From the set of available layers several Widgets can be created combining them.

Other important technological aspects of the Dashboard are how it supports multi-tenancy, multi-language and real-time. Multi-tenancy means the support of multiple cities / locations while limiting each user to access only visualisations of the cities the user has access to (can be one or more). The data of each city is segment in its own database to increase security and better manage and organize information. Real-time is supported by making direct use of the TANGENT API AMQP Broker and using its subscriptions to notify the Dashboard when data changes in any of the data sources that are currently active. Even calculated data, such as the one behind Indicators / KPIs uses this mechanism, only it binds to a set of topics associated with the sources of the calculated data.

Planning and Incident Management

The TANGENT Tool implementation of Planning and Incident Management features, which were introduced in the description of the TANGENT Tool, is at an early stage. Development is progressing quickly because these features are based on the existing visualisation features already used for the Dashboard Widgets and on the core Simulation features that have been under development from early in the TANGENT project. Future publications

will explore in more detail the user interface and workflows supported by the TANGENT Tool and how these features can solve complex inter-organizational problems, resulting in globally optimised transport networks.

Conclusions

A new group of Traffic Management tools, called Next Generation Traffic Management Systems, has been introduced recently to describe an evolution of Traffic Management systems that focused on a single vertical like a motorway operator or agency. These tools usually bring different vertical systems together, such as traffic lights operation, traffic control and bus monitoring. The TANGENT Tool is going a step further and aims at unifying traffic and transport operations across agencies managing the different vertical systems. By adopting forecast and simulation technology it is possible to extend the capabilities of operators and managers, automatically identifying predefined anomalies, providing a Common Operational Picture (COP), proposing a Response Plan that can be applied to solve these anomalies and accompany the monitoring as the situation is solved, and beyond. This is why we are proposing a new, broader category of tools called Next Generation Traffic and Transport Management Systems. We believe this new category of tools will allow urban areas to achieve a next level of unified transportation management that is required to achieve the demanding environmental and societal needs of the decades ahead.

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